

The logo for EVOLVE2CARE features a large, light blue, rounded shape on the left. To its right is a stylized blue wave with a white crest, and below the wave is a series of seven dark blue circles of varying sizes, arranged in a slightly curved line.

EVOLVE2CARE

**Barriers and Drivers to Innovation
in Transitional Care**

Funded by
the European Union

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Brief Preface

The EVOLVE2CARE project conducted an exploratory study to identify the key barriers and drivers influencing the introduction of innovation in transitional care. To achieve this, a narrative review of the existing literature was first performed to identify and analyze the documented barriers and drivers related to innovation uptake in this context. Building on these findings, an online survey was designed and distributed through the partners' networks.

A total of **75 participants completed the survey**, representing a diverse range of stakeholders, including innovators (36), accelerators and investors (6), living labs (8), end-users such as care units, hospitals, and practitioners (11), individual end-users (10), policymakers and regulatory bodies (2), and representatives of EU initiatives (2). Participants came from 17 EU Member States, 4 associated countries, and 12 non-EU countries, ensuring a broad and inclusive perspective.

Survey respondents were also invited to provide their contact details if they were willing to participate in a follow-up interview. The interview phase explored in greater depth the insights that emerged from the survey results, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the factors shaping innovation in transitional care. In total, **39 interviews were conducted** with innovators (8), accelerators and investors (2), living labs (4), end-users from care units, hospitals, and practitioners (7), individual end-users (7), policymakers and regulatory bodies (2), and representatives of EU initiatives (2). The interview participants represented 5 EU Member States, 4 associated countries, and 1 non-EU country.

Figure 1. Overview of Methodology Followed

Key outcomes

Barriers to Innovation

Regulatory Challenges:

- The complexity and variability of regulatory frameworks hinder the rapid deployment of new technologies. Lengthy approval processes and fragmented regional regulations exacerbate delays.
- Innovators seek harmonised regulations to balance safety with the flexibility needed for innovation.

Funding and Financial Constraints:

- Financial challenges include securing sustainable funding and navigating reimbursement systems.
- Startups face difficulties in moving from prototypes to scalable solutions due to limited investment.

Technology Integration and Interoperability:

- Existing healthcare systems often struggle to integrate new technologies due to interoperability issues and the lack of standardisation. While innovators focus on technical alignment, end-users emphasise usability and accessibility.

Key Drivers of Innovation

Regulatory Support and Flexibility:

- A supportive and adaptive regulatory environment is essential for fostering innovation. Regulatory drivers include incentives for compliance, flexible frameworks, and policy alignment with emerging technologies.
- Stakeholders universally agree on the importance of streamlined regulations to facilitate technology adoption, especially in home care and AI-driven solutions.

Technological Advancements:

- Wearable devices, AI, and telemedicine are transforming transitional care. Innovations in predictive analytics and real-time monitoring enhance patient-centred care and efficiency.

- Digital tools such as remote monitoring and telehealth are pivotal in addressing accessibility challenges.

Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement:

- Collaboration among healthcare providers, patients, researchers, and developers drives successful innovation.
- Co-designing solutions and leveraging feedback loops through pilot projects are critical for refining and scaling technologies.